

ASSESSING THE PHYSICAL AND MENTAL HEALTH COMPLICATIONS OF POST-COVID-19 PATIENTS IN BANGLADESH

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1. INTRODUCTION

Contagious diseases, a historical challenging (Zafri et al., 2021), have recently manifested in the global disruption caused by COVID-19, impacting lives worldwide, including Bangladesh (Hosen et al., 2021). Despite prompt actions by the Government of Bangladesh (GoB), the virus spread, affecting over 2 million individuals, with recovery and death tolls documented by USAID. Recovered individual may experience short and long-term physical health complications, while mental health issues, especially among the students and economically disadvantaged mothers, persist post-COVID-19 (Ehsan & Jahan, 2022; Hosen et al., 2021; Islam et al., 2021). This study, based on qualitative data from a questionnaire survey on 100 COVID-19 patients in Bangladesh and secondary sources. Data analysis involved visual presentation through graphs and charts, and correlation analysis was conducted using Karl Pearson's coefficient. The result were presented in a clear and concise manner for better understanding. The study aims to uncover physical and mental complications, emphasizing the need for integrated health strategies to address the pandemic's enduring impact (Shanbehzadeh et al., 2021; Hosen et al., 2021).

2. KEY FINDINGS

2.1 Physical and mental complications of Post-COVID-19 patients

Post-COVID-19, participants experienced physical complications like hair loss (46%), dizziness (27%), palpitations (26%), and loss of appetite (25%). Mental complications included depression (59%), anxiety (55%), and memory problems (51%).

2.2 Physical and Mental Health Status Pre and Post-COVID-19

Post-COVID-19, there was a shift in physical health categories, with a decrease in 'high' and an increase in 'moderate'. Mental health also shifted, showing an increase in 'moderate' and a decrease in 'high', indicating a move towards greater equilibrium.

2.3 Correlation between Physical and Mental Health Complications

A correlation analysis revealed a moderate correlation (0.54) between physical and mental health complications of post-COVID-19 patients. The findings indicated that as physical health improved, mental health tended to improve with compromised physical health were more susceptible to mental health challenges.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The study emphasizes the enduring physical and mental complications faced by post-COVID-19 patients in Bangladesh. Recommendations include comprehensive

healthcare approaches, mental health support, and public awareness to address these challenges effectively.

Figure 1. Correlation between Physical and Mental Health Complications of Post-COVID-19 patients

Figure 2. Correlation between Physical and Mental Health Complications of Post-COVID-19 patients

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